

ABOUT APPLICATION OF GEOINFORMATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM AND COMMUNICATION OBJECTS OF THE STATE CADASTR

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ABSTRACT

The article describes the content of the organization of geoinformatics and GIS technologies; establishment; communication of cadastral and its use in educational system; the content of new “Geoinformatics” educational literature in masters outlined.

KEYWORDS: geoinformatics, cadastre, education, communication-GIS, cartography, geo visualization, Arc GIS database, database, TEMPUS program.

INTRODUCTION

At the present time, the database is regarded as the manufacturing industry in geoinformatics, its bank and management, a variety of purposes aimed to solve the problems of geographic information systems (GIS), including the preparation of hardware and software products. GIS — geoinformation technology will be used as a shell application. GIS technologies are used in a variety of areas in their public, including the Ministry of Land Resources, Geodesy, Cartography and Cadastral State Committee proceedings in all the land tasks, architecture, building three-dimensional models, remote astronomical observations, distance research of the earth, etc. Experts have conducted a lot of research by applying geographic information systems.

GIS technology is being used not only in the state cadastral proceedings, but also in the formation of a database and the creation of digital cards; in general, every cadastral sector is doing research to create its own compatible GIS. This unified system shows that the coordinates of the areas of digital cards should fall on top of each other when state cadastrals provide its objects to the State Cadastral system. This article discusses cadastral GIS technologies and its application in education and training systems.

Cadastral of communication objects lists following objects and look at it as an object of study: international, intercity, important regional and local telephone and telegraph networks, fixed equipment, transmission lines, etc. At the same time roads and railways are also cadastral object. To input cadastral data and preceding its system on the process of creation of “Communication GIS” Geographic Information system can be imagined as follows.

To perform cadastral system’s duties, collection regional data, storage, search, analyze and illustrate, to understand database via a computer management system complete tools of ArcGIS are recommended.

Figure 1. in ArcGIS program topographic for nomenclature square

To input cartographical data into GIS each object in the present paper map is numbered as a separate layer. Before numbering task topographic maps are selected then they are scanned at 300 dpi TIF format color volume and placed in the computer memory in raster form. To repair scanning errors the map schemes are corrected on Adobe Photoshop graphics editor, they are brought into the same size and cut. After completion of cutting task maps are uploaded to Arc GIS software. In Arc GIS program first and foremost task begins by choosing the base points, in this step angular coordinates of trapeze topographical map are used. Trapeze topographical maps are called by their nomenclature.

Figure 3. Createion of nomenclature square ArcGIS program

For trapeze which was created for the GIS program, corresponding topographic sheets of maps are inserted, and this is performed by using “add” icon (equipment) on the Arc GIS program. After receiving the map sheets from Fold equipment “added layer” function is selected. Then from “Spatial Reference” section “Fit to the displayed extent” function is selected and is carried out by adding new maps to the previous maps. At the same time, a new layer is placed on its Trapeze and “transformation” task is performed. A new map process is performed again the above-mentioned procedure.

After creation of trapeze of topographical maps each type of object in the map is numbered as a separate layer. Creation of layers of object types is carried out through “Layers”, they are saved with the name of the object (Figure 4). The results of the work performed in the Arc GIS program, attached cartographic,

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